

THE IMPACT OF GASTRONOMIC TOURISM ON THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The article discusses the current state of gastronomic tourism, which is defined as a trip to get acquainted with the national cuisine of the country, the features of cooking, training and raising the level of professional knowledge in the field of cooking, the role of culinary tourism in the development and promotion of the destination brand.

Key words: *tourism, gastronomic tourism, gastronomic tours, gastronomic brand, destination, promotion methods, tourist resources.*

JEL: Z33, Q51, F61

Tourism losses for the ten months of 2021 amounted to \$935 billion. According to the World Tourism Organization at the UN, the economic indicators of the industry have rolled back to the period of the late 1990s - early 2000s. Domestic tourism continues to develop. Nevertheless, the usual understanding of travel will change, as will the development of the entire industry.

Today's trends, which fully reflect the daily processes of human existence, include the popularization and growth of interest in nutrition, since for a long-time everyday culture has been mainly considered in the aspect of descriptive studies of everyday life, in particular, housing, clothing, the principles of house studies, organization of trade, leisure, traditional customs and norms. Interest in food as a component of everyday culture was mainly auxiliary in research.

Studies of food culture allow us to look at various aspects of human life from a different angle, including the organization of tourist activities and the development of such a type of food tourism.

According to the World Food Travel Association, gastronomic tourism is a unique and memorable experience of food and drinks.

Gastronomic tourism is a type of tourism, the main purpose of which is to get acquainted with the cuisine of a certain region. Gastronomic tourism is closely related to rural tourism, which also has a culinary component.

There are several definitions that make it possible to classify travel as this type of tourism. Food, tasting, culinary, food, wine, beer are all kinds of gastronomic tourism.

Gastronomic tourism is tourism where tourists and visitors who plan to partially or completely taste the cuisine of a certain area or carry out activities related to gastronomy visit certain destinations.

Gastronomic tourism is a trip to get acquainted with the national cuisine of the country, the peculiarities of production and preparation of products and dishes, as well as training and improvement of professional knowledge. Today, it is gastronomic tourism that has become one of the fastest growing innovative areas of tourism. People are looking for an experience based on regional peculiarities and culture in travel. Gastronomic tourism can also be considered as a branch of tourism aimed at the development and promotion of food and drinks as objects of attracting tourists.

Travelers interested in food, wine and beer, cooking or baking, as well as the history of some products and dishes, can choose today from a variety of culinary tourist destinations, which are presented on numerous sites around the world the right tourist product. A culinary tour is a specially

selected program of culinary recreation, including tasting of dishes and drinks, familiarization with the technology and process of their preparation, as well as training with professional chefs. Depending on the purpose of the trip, the tour may include all the above points, several events or one specific segment of the culinary tour. In recent years, gastronomic tours include visits to various culinary festivals, holidays and fairs.

The target audience of gastronomic tours includes:

- tourists who want to join the culture of the country through its national cuisine;
- gourmet tourists. "Gourme" is a person with high demands for food and refined taste.

Unlike him, a gourmet is a person who just likes a lot and delicious food. These two concepts are often confused in the literature.

- tourists using a culinary tour for training and professional skills (cooks, sommeliers, baristas, tasters, restaurateurs);
- representatives of travel agencies traveling to explore this tourist destination.

The development and promotion of gastronomy, authentic products and dishes are significant tools for identification, competitiveness and promotion of the territory, so the study of this phenomenon as an element of the formation of a favorable image and promotion of a regional brand is relevant.

The gastronomic brand is a very strong "magnet" for tourists. Attractive culinary images are associated with extremely pleasant sensations, so they are easy to remember and often cause to return to a certain region again and again. National cuisine is a way to get acquainted with the local culture, reflects the character and mentality of the local population.

In the collection "Food Nations" researchers note that national cuisines can be most important for people who are able to benefit most from their creation, namely: politicians, food marketers and other nutritionists, as national branding companies are gaining momentum in an effort to increase the value of their products.

In order for national cuisine to act as a powerful magnet for attracting tourists, a number of conditions for the successful positioning of national cuisine must be met: the traditional attachment of the nation to certain food, the presence of regional food preferences, the authenticity of cuisine, the variety of national dishes, the existence of national legends, health benefits, the availability of an assortment of specialties that

Gastronomy includes all traditional values associated with new trends in tourism: respect for culture and traditions, for a healthy lifestyle, for new experiences.

Gastronomic tourism is an acquaintance with the traditional cuisine of a particular area, accessible to any tourist, not just the lot of the chosen ones. And since enjoying the taste of food is available to much more people than the true pleasure of contemplating the beauty of architecture, fine arts and even nature, the creation of a strong gastronomic brand certainly becomes a serious factor in increasing the influx of tourists. Cooking can become the main motive for choosing the direction of travel.

Thanks to the presence of gastronomic brands, the territory becomes additionally known, and branded products become an integral part of the image of a particular area.

Let's consider the components of the gastronomic brand:

- well-developed field of gastronomy;
- energetic gastronomic community with traditional restaurants and chefs;
- local ingredients used in traditional cuisine;
- local know-how in cooking;
- traditional food markets and food industry;
- gastronomic festivals, awards, competitions;
- respect for the environment;
- promotion of gastronomy to educational institutions.

At the same time, there can be no fresh and anonymous products in gastronomic branding - they must have individuality, otherwise the brand will become vulnerable and delocalized. Thus, it is very important to identify traditional and natural resources that will be turned into tourist products that can be associated with a particular region.

Many countries purposefully design their own gastronomic face, an example is the experience of Singapore, where the so-called new Asian cuisine was created. There are also spontaneous brands of territories (in France, Italy, Spain), although in conditions of fierce competition from other countries, the use of aggressive strategies by new players, the reputation of even such culinary gurus requires support programs. For example, the Spanish authorities are actively promoting their seemingly very popular cuisine.

In its gastronomic tourism report, the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) posted the results of the survey among the current members of its organization (156 countries). According to the results of this survey, 88.2% of respondents consider gastronomy a strategic element in determining the brand and image of the region and only 11.8% of respondents consider it an important aspect.

Nevertheless, only 67.6% of respondents believe that a unique gastronomic brand has been formed in their country, 32.3% believe that their country has significant potential for the development of this direction.

The Republic of Moldova has all the prerequisites to become a tourist attraction, namely, a country of gastronomic tourism.

Conclusion. In modern society, preferences are changing, and gastronomic tourism is developing rapidly. This type of tourism contributes to the socio-economic development of the country, including the creation of additional jobs, the preservation or opening of production of individual products, as well as their implementation, helps the branding of regions, attract tourist flows.

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